

ISic1273

I.Sicily inscription 1273

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

brick

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Motta S. Anastasia (part of chora of Katania)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140762

1. [ἱερατεύσασαν τᾶς Ἄφ]ροδίτας
2. [τὰν δεῖνα — —]στράτου
3. [ἀνέθηκεν ἂ β]ουλὰ καὶ
4. [ὁ δᾶμος τᾶι Ἄφρο]δίται.
- 5.

Edition: PHI333197

1. [ἐπὶ ἱερείας τᾶς Ἄφ]ροδίτας
2. [τᾶς δεῖνος τᾶς Νικο(?)]στράτου
3. [ὁ δεῖνα τοῦ δεῖνος, Ἄρχεβ(?)]ούλα καὶ
4. [ἡ δεῖνα — — — Ἄφρο]δίται.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492879

EDCS 39101642

PHI 140762

PHI 333197

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0448 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 45.1374

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5652

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 5235

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